

Building a Face Recognition System and Verifying Identity Using Aadhaar Authentication

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Abstract : Face recognition technology within biometrics is one of many methods that may be used to verify and authenticate persons. All three branches of government, as well as law enforcement and the private sector, make use of this surveillance and security technology to monitor and control access. It has many applications presently, and no doubt more are being discovered all the time. In this paper, we develop a face recognition system that enables the identification and verification of the individuals using Aadhaar authentication.

Keywords:

Face Recognition, Verification, Security Technology, Aadhaar Authentication

1. INTRODUCTION

The number of fields that could gain from FRT is expanding as a result of significant scientific and industrial breakthroughs. In order to analyse the FRT market, numerous publications have segmented the information they gathered [1] [3]. It has been determined that healthcare, marketing/retail, and security/law enforcement are the three most crucial FRT application areas at the present time [2].

To begin, facial recognition CCTV systems, which are used to identify and track criminals or find missing children, and identity authentication security systems, which are used in both public and private settings (including mobile phones, homes, airports, and government buildings), are essential components of security and law enforcement (such as airports, banks, schools, hotels, etc.) [3]-[5].

Second, in the realm of medicine, some of the most crucial applications are tracking patient drug use, identifying genetic disorders like DiGeorge syndrome, and refining methods of pain management [6]. In the case of COVID-19 in particular, FRT has been used for both case detection and contact tracking [7].

Third, in the realm of marketing and retail, the most widely used applications include facial recognition payments, consumer behaviour analysis to enhance shopping experiences, and data collection to deliver individualised offerings [8] [9]. However, it is expected that the FRT market will grow to encompass additional industries in the near future as the number of technical applications grows. Some markets that fit this description are the automotive sector and the smart home industry [10].

2. BACKGROUND

Early FRT perception polls, on the other hand, only compared the public acceptance of a selection of FRT applications, rather than isolating the FRT apps that are thought to be more prone to misuse [11]. Members of the general public may have a vastly different understanding of the programme internal examples than the programmers themselves [12].

As an example, experts have pinpointed three common pillars of confidence in automated systems [13]. The three pillars are effectiveness, efficiency, and meaning. The term process is used to describe the way automation is run, whereas the term performance describes what the automation is capable of doing [14]. In this context, purpose alludes to the motivations behind the rise of mechanisation (the reasons for automation development). Therefore, comparing public viewpoints on multiple FRT applications is not sufficient, as the automation trust model demonstrates that the public may observe these traits in the internal instances of FRT apps and produce varying levels of trust [15]. This is because these characteristics may be seen in internal FRT app instances, leading to varied degrees of trust among the general audience. Law enforcement agencies can employ FRT for a variety of purposes, such as tracking down missing children or analysing data from widespread surveillance operations [16]. These

two cases may be perceived differently by the general public since they were designed for different purposes and are applied in different ways [17].

On the other hand, there are constraints to analysing how the public views FRT by only listing examples of FRT apps, as some characteristics may be shared by several FRT applications. Because of progress in both technology and infrastructure, the FRT sector will also continue to grow and penetrate new markets. To address the issues the public has encountered in some FRT scenarios and to benefit FRT long-term growth, it is required to break FRT application examples into unique scenarios based on certain principles in order to compare the public reactions to each scenario. This is necessary to solve problems people have run across when using FRT in specific situations. [18]-[25].

3. PROPOSED METHOD

An important goal of this research was to create a public perception model that may be used by FRT creators and legal experts to spot scenarios in which the technology could be misused. First, we compiled a list of features included in several FRT applications that the average person would recognise. Next, we used these broad categories to divide the possible and existing FRT applications into a wide variety of narrower ones. Finally, we chose three major characteristics that have been shown to have an effect on FRT adoption from previous research in order to characterise public opinion which is shown in Fig 1.

After a face has been identified in a given frame, the image undergoes pre-processing, which includes noise reduction and the removal of unnecessary information. The feature extraction process follows, and it is at this point that the classifier becomes useful. When the real-time image has been processed, it is compared against archived images that have also been processed. When a possible match is made, the photos are checked against a local watch list database to determine the person criminal or suspicious history. The length of time he was captured on video will be detailed in the case that he is a criminal or suspect. If it turns out the person is not a citizen, the photo is checked against a global database of criminals who are wanted by authorities. If a match is made, the amount of time the suspect was subject to camera surveillance will be recorded. He is judged innocent because the two lists contain no common information.

Figure 1: Proposed Model

In this study, we examine two distinct methods for identifying rotating objects. In the first approach, multiple iterations of the first XML file are used to feed the image into the initial classifier from different vantage points. This is followed by the second approach. The alternative method entails duplicating the original XML file and using that duplicate to create new XML files. Multiple recently developed classifiers use the XML files that were generated to identify certain objects inside an image.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Although equivalent services can be obtained from other software packages, this one offers a number of benefits that could ultimately be good for society as a whole. It is feasible that, given the complexity of its development and the revelations it has made, automated facial identification technology will be challenging to recognise. A user-friendly interface that necessitates minimal effort on the part of the user is likewise feasible to give. The user need only provide an input in the form of a photograph that is updated in real time for this system to carry out the remaining arduous image processing activities. Any skilled programmer can make changes and add new features to the project because it is open source. This paradigm fundamental simplicity makes it applicable in a wide variety of contexts which shown in Fig 2 and Fig 3.

Figure 2: Accuracy of FRT

Figure 3: Error Rate

5. CONCLUSIONS

The proposed facial recognition technology will be put into use. The system can correctly recognise faces even if the input image does not match the set of photographs of the individual that are kept in the database. The algorithm needs to extract and calculate the main components of the image before it can tell how unlike the input image is to the saved photos. This means that the newly generated face image used for recognition can be tweaked somewhat before being put into use. Since smaller images that contain the essential features require the

least processing to train the wavelets, this has a positive effect on computing cost, recognition accuracy, and discriminatory power. The most notable benefit is that we leverage an already-existing database of citizens.

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